

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Assessment of Delivery of Basic Government Services of Seal of Good Local Governance (SGLG) Awardees in the Province of Pangasinan

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Abstract

This study utilized the descriptive-survey method of research. The primary source of data is the survey questionnaire administered to three (3) groups of respondents. The study was conducted in Pangasinan involving eight (8) municipalities who have been SGLG Awardees for three (3) consecutive years. The respondents of this study were barangay officials, community residents, LGU employees and department heads. The data collected were tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted using various statistical tools using frequency, percentage, and weighted mean. To determine the significant difference in the responses of the three (3) groups of respondents, the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used with Statistics Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 17.0.

Findings revealed that the delivery of basic government services in the areas of Agriculture, Environment and Natural Resources, Housing, Public Works, Public Buildings and Other Facilities, Social Welfare and Development, Information and Communication System, Tourism Facilities, and Other Services and Facilities were assessed by the respondents to be of Moderate Extent. Only the Health Service was assessed by the three (3) groups of respondents as delivered to the Full Extent. Results further revealed that there is no significant difference in the assessment of the three (3) groups of respondents on the extent of delivery of basic services of the SGLG LGU Awardees in the province of Pangasinan.

Relative to challenges faced by the SGLG LGU Awardees in the delivery of basic services, the respondents identified a lack of public involvement in municipal planning and programs as the main challenge while inaccessibility of community for services was the least challenges faced by the SGLG LGU Awardees. The correlation analysis implies that there is a negative relationship between the delivery of services and the challenges faced by the SGLG LGU awardees

Keywords: SGLG Awardee; Reservist; EO 70; Capability Development; Command and Control

1. Introduction

In 1991, Republic Act No. 7160, otherwise known as the Local Government Code was enacted into law, transferring control and responsibility of delivering basic services to the hands of local government units (LGU). The goal is to upgrade the allocation of services at the grassroots level and to ameliorate the efficiency in the allocation of resources. Also, it hopes to expand the decision-making capacity by motivating the stakeholders to enjoy, especially at the local level (www.senate.gov.ph).

In order to further strengthen accountability at the LGU level, DILG introduced the Seal of Good Local Governance (SGLG) in 2014 through then DILG Secretary Mar Roxas, which a derived and refined version of the Seal of Good Housekeeping. This denotes good performance and integrity with the use of sustained local development and continued governance reforms. It is a progressive and enhanced mode of assessment to set forth distinction on the performance

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of the LGUs in several areas. (DILG Memorandum Circular No. 2018-49) The original SGLG had six (6) fundamental elements: 1) peace and order; 2) financial administration; 3) business friendliness and competitiveness; 4) social protection; 5) disaster preparedness; and 6) environment management.

By 2040, *A Matatag, Maginhawa, at Panatag na Buhay* will be achieved if the foundation for a resilient and high-trust society, inclusive growth, and a globally-competitive knowledge economy by 2022. There are three (3) pillars that will support this goal, namely: *Malasakit, Pagbabago, and Patuloy na Pag-unlad*, which are further assisted by macroeconomic fundamentals and strategic policies, and erected on a solid bedrock of infrastructure, safety, healthy environment, peace, and security.

With the criteria in measuring good governance set in place by the Department of Interior and Local Government (DILG), the researcher assessed the delivery of devolved basic government services of the LGUs who have been SGLG Awardees in the Province of Pangasinan as perceived by three groups of respondents, the Community Residents, Barangay Officials, and the LGU Employees. The study wanted to know if there were changes or improvements in the delivery of government services after the LGUs have been given the Seal of Good Local Governance for three (3) consecutive years.

2. Methodology

2.1. Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive-survey method of research. The principal source of data is the survey questionnaire to be administered to three (3) groups of respondents.

Problem Statement number 1 and 3 were answered using descriptive method with frequency distribution, percentage, and weighted mean as the statistical tool while Problem Statement number 2 was answered using ANOVA and problem statement number 4 was answered through the survey questionnaire utilizing Pearson Product Moment of Correlation computed through the use of SPSS Version 17.0.

2.2. Research Locale

The study was conducted in Pangasinan involving eight (8) municipalities who have been SGLG Awardees for three (3) consecutive years, to wit: Alcala, Balungao, Bayambang, Infanta, Lingayen, San Nicolas, Tayug, and Villasis. Four (4) barangays were chosen from these identified municipalities to participate in the survey.

2.3. Research Participants

There were five (5) respondents of this study, who are the barangay officials from each barangay, and five (5) community residents from 32 barangays of the eight (8) localities in the province of Pangasinan giving a total of 320 respondents. Added to it are 10 LGU employees and department heads from the eight (8) localities numbering 80, which gives a total of 400 respondents.

2.4. Research Instrument

The research instrument is a survey questionnaire. Part I focuses on the delivery of basic government services, the indicators were taken from the list of devolved basic services mentioned in the Local Government Code of 1991 while Part II deals with the challenges faced by local government units in the delivery of basic government services, the indicators were researcher-made items.

2.5. Data Gathering Procedure

The instrument was tried out to the five (5) employees, five (5) barangay officials, and five (5) residents of Mapandan, Pangasinan, a locality not involved in this study to test for reliability.

The researcher sought permission from the Provincial DILG Officer and the Provincial ABC President to administer the questionnaire to the concerned localities. Further, several letters of request were also given to the Chief Executive of the local government units involved in the study.

After reliability was established and permission was given by the higher authorities for the conduct of the study, the researcher personally went around the eight localities. Distribution of the questionnaire took two (2) days. However, the retrieval took four weeks due to the onset of typhoons and rainy season. Bayambang was the last municipality to be

retrieved that took four weeks. Nonetheless, data gathering was completed in 45 days. 373 out of 400 questionnaires were retrieved from the respondents giving a retrieval rate of 93%.

2.6. Ethical Considerations

This research study followed ethical guidelines. The study considered three (3) ethical issues into account. These include the informed consent, information confidentiality as defined by the Data Privacy Act of 2012, and the researcher's role and responsibilities. In order to build trust and confidence between the researcher and the respondents, the researcher personally informed the respondents of the intended purpose of the study and the nondisclosure of their identities.

3. Results and discussion

Based on results, the responses of the three groups of respondents are comparable with each other. The LGUs, barangay officials, and the residents all regarded that the SGLG LGU awardees in Pangasinan (overall Mean = 3.02 for all the respondents group) moderately provide local service delivery in all the indicators given. The respondents indicated a Moderate Extent response in terms of government service delivery by the LGUs in Pangasinan across the indicators except in health, which they regard as Full Extent of service delivery.

Table 1 Extent of Delivery of Government Services by the SGLG LGU Awardees in Pangasinan n = 372

Indicator	Extent of Service Delivery Weighted Mean (Verbal Description)			Mean	Rank
	LGU (N=74)	Barangay Officials (N = 150)	Residents (N=148)		
Agriculture	3.01 (ME)	2.95 (ME)	2.88 (ME)	2.95 (ME)	7.5
Environment and Natural Resources	3.04 (ME)	2.94 (ME)	2.90 (ME)	2.96 (ME)	6
Health	3.40 (FE)	3.42 (FE)	3.44 (FE)	3.42 (FE)	1
Housing	2.53 (ME)	2.65 (ME)	2.74 (ME)	2.64 (ME)	10
Public Works	2.92 (ME)	2.95 (ME)	2.90 (ME)	2.93 (ME)	9
Public Buildings and Other Facilities	3.28 (FE)	3.14 (ME)	3.15 (ME)	3.19 (ME)	2
Social Welfare and Development	3.03 (ME)	3.11 (ME)	3.06 (ME)	3.06 (ME)	4
Information and Communication System	2.96 (ME)	3.02 (ME)	2.95 (ME)	2.98 (ME)	5
Tourism Facilities	2.90 (ME)	2.90 (ME)	3.04 (ME)	2.95 (ME)	7.5
Other Services and Facilities	3.09 (ME)	3.10 (ME)	3.11 (ME)	3.10 (ME)	3
Mean	3.02	3.02	3.02	3.02	
Verbal Description	Moderate Extent	Moderate Extent	Moderate Extent	Moderate Extent	

Verbal Description: 3.26-4.00 (Full Extent, FE), 2.51-3.25 (Moderate Extent, ME), 1.76-2.50 (Little Extent, LE), 1.0-1.75 (None at all, NAA)

It was also revealed that the three groups of respondents consider that the overall service delivery of the ten government basic services was provided to a Moderate Extent. This was indicated with a weighted mean of 3.02.

The area on Health was ranked first by the respondents with an overall weighted mean of 3.42 and with a verbal description of Full Extent. The residents have rated this area as Full Extent with 3.44, followed by barangay officials with 3.42 and by the LGUs with 3.40. This may be so because the recipients of the health services are the community residents themselves. This may also be contributed by the active involvement of the Barangay Health Workers and the Rural Health Units in the different localities.

The health care program remains as one of the top priority programs of the provincial government of Pangasinan. This was revealed in former Governor Amado T. Espino, Jr in his report in the State of the Province in 2014, where he revealed

the yearly increased of its budget allocation from P307.9 million in 2008 to P670 million in 2014. Espino also took pride in the upgrading of the diagnostic capability of all 14 government-owned hospitals, which are now equipped with automated laboratory diagnostic equipment, digital x-ray, hemodialysis machines, with Pangasinan Provincial Hospital being provided with CT scan and gas sterilizer apart from other modern equipment. All of these 14 government-owned hospitals have been ISO-Certified (Province of Pangasinan Official Website, 2014).

Public buildings and other facilities obtained a weighted mean of 3.19 having a verbal description of Moderate Extent. It can be seen from the table that the LGUs have given a higher rating of 3.28 as compared to the barangay officials (3.14) and community residents (3.15) since the LGUs are more aware of the existence and operation of these public buildings. The barangay officials and community residents believed that there are buildings and facilities that are yet to be built for public services.

A public building is any type of building that is available to the public and is financed from public sources. Categorically, public structures are funded through local tariffs by the national and local government units. All public buildings usually house the different governmental offices. Public buildings typically are used to provide service to the public. Among the public buildings that provide free services to residents are libraries, public schools, post offices, and court houses (VanBaren, 2019).

The results further showed that the eight (8) LGUs who were SGLG awardees have not fully provided the needed public buildings and facilities required by the Local Government Code. One of the localities that do not have yet a functional fire station and substation is the Municipality of Alcala. Municipal jails are also not existent in most localities where prisoners are brought to the Provincial Jail in Lingayen after conviction.

The third area in the generated weighted mean is Other Services and Facilities with a weighted mean of 3.10 described as Moderate Extent. This include services and facilities that cover those involving hygiene and sanitation, solid waste collection, transportation facilities, education, police, and fire services, among others. For this item, the community residents have indicated a higher weighted mean of 3.11 while close behind are the barangay officials (3.10) and the LGUs (3.09). The Solid Waste Management Act of 2000 is one of the issues that are covered by this government service. There are issues of waste segregation and garbage collection that are affecting some barangays. The responsibility of waste collection also came into focus as to who is responsible for addressing it, whether the LGU or the barangay. This problem remains to be addressed by the concerned local officials.

As of January 2010, only three (3) out of Pangasinan's 44 towns and four (4) cities have built sanitary landfills. However, the Provincial Environment and Natural Resources Officer have encouraged the LGUs to cluster together since sanitary landfills costs at least P100M to construct (Cardinoza, 2010).

Fourth in rank is the area on Social Welfare and Development with 3.06 overall weighted mean and verbal description of Moderate Extent. The barangay officials have rated this area higher than the other two groups of respondents with 3.11 while the residents gave it 3.06 and the LGUs with 3.03.

The evolution of the purpose of the Kalahi-CIDSS is to ensure that barangays/communities of targeted municipalities be qualified to accomplish improved access to services and to take part in more inclusive budgeting, local planning, and implementation. This accomplishment could be the reason why the barangay officials had a higher rating in terms of delivery of social welfare and development services than the other two groups of respondents.

Information and Communication System (ICS) came in fifth rank with an overall weighted mean of 2.98 and having a verbal description of Moderate Extent. From the three groups of respondents, the barangay officials had a higher rating of 3.02 as compared to the LGUs (2.96) and residents (2.95), respectively. The result implies that the provision of the ICS in the different localities have yet to be improved since their ratings are not distant from each other.

In October 2018, the Digital Cities Philippines Awards gave various recognitions to the Municipality of Bayambang one of which is winning first place for the Best in eGov Systems for Global Competitiveness (G2W). Bayambang also won Second place award in Best in eGov Digital Finance Empowerment (P2G), and third place in the Best in eGov Customer Empowerment (G2C) (Philippine News Agency, 2018).

Sixth is the area on Environment and Natural Resources, where the overall weighted mean is 2.96 with a verbal description of Moderate Extent. The LGUs showed a higher weighted mean of 3.01 (Moderate Extent), while the barangay officials and community residents revealed their ratings of 2.95 (ME) and 2.88 (ME), respectively. The result could be due to the fact that four (4) of the eight localities involved in this study have forest reservoirs, namely:

Balungao, Infanta, San Fabian, and San Nicolas. The respondents were specifically concerned with the implementation of the community-based forestry projects.

As mentioned by Tacio (2013), the Philippines was nearly engulfed with forest resources dispensed throughout the 30 million hectares more than 90 years ago. These assets provided employment, income, medicine, water, building materials, and food as well as a healthy environment. As mentioned by the Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR), only three-fourths of the archipelago was covered with forest during the 1950s. This figure had shrunk to half in 1972, and in 1988, only one-fourth was wooded while one tiny fraction of this still maintains as a virgin forest. The United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) stated that the Philippines still have forested areas covering 7,665,000 hectares. The country lost an average of 54,750 hectares per year between the periods of 1990 and 2010 (Tacio, 2013).

Tied for the same spot is the area on Agriculture and Tourism Facilities with overall weighted mean scores of 2.95 and verbal description of Moderate Extent. Under Agriculture, the LGUs have claimed to deliver this service to a Moderate Extent with a weighted mean of 3.01, while the barangay officials rated this with a 2.95 weighted mean, and the residents yielded a weighted mean of 2.88.

It was revealed further that the three groups of respondents have a common observation in the enforcement of fishery laws in municipal waters. Although Lingayen is the only coastal town from the list of involved localities; however, the other municipalities are consumers of products from the sea. The result was probably because fish products from the sea that are caught and harvested using dynamite fishing are being delivered to their municipal markets.

In 2013, the LGU of San Fabian sought the help of the Philippine Coast Guard because of reported illegal activities in their municipal waters. Some retired law enforcers are operating trawl fishing boats that are reported fishing in their area. Trawling is also considered destructive because fishing nets that are dragged by fishing boats catch even small fish and hit and damage corals. While trawls may be expensive, explosives used to blast fish are easy to make, and the materials are readily available. Some fishermen themselves manufacture explosives and would teach anyone who cares to learn. The illegal fishers may not be armed, but they can use the explosive to threaten law enforcers (Sotelo, 2015).

Further, Tourism Facilities revealed that the residents provided a higher rating of 3.04 as compared to the 2.90 weighted mean for both the LGUs and the barangay officials. In the circumstances of sustainable development, the local government units play key roles on the success of its local tourism industry, including a powerful impact in safeguarding its resources. Sustainable tourism development points out to the management of all government assets that meets the demands of tourists while preserving the opportunities for the times ahead, in such a way that aesthetic, social and economic needs can be satisfied while maintaining essential ecological processes, biological diversity, cultural integrity, and life support systems (Tourism Act of 2010).

More important to this perspective is the participation in a full range by the stakeholders and the community in the planning and decision-making process in order to identify the long-term interest of the community. In this context, the local government can have an overwhelming influence on the local tourism industry and join in conserving the resources on which its future depends. Further, the institutional capacity of the local government to yield for tourism development will be strained by several issues, including financial and physical resources, individual capacities, governance, and community acceptance (Javier and Elazigue, 2011).

The area pertaining to Public Works/Infrastructure was ranked 2nd from the bottom with an overall weighted mean of 2.93 and a verbal description of Moderate Extent. Despite the Duterte government's BUILD-BUILD-BUILD scheme, the respondents have yet to see the delivery of the public works and infrastructure in their respective localities by their local government units. It can be seen from the table that the assessment of the three groups of respondents is not distant from each other, where barangay officials generated a weighted mean of 2.95, LGUs with 2.92, and the residents with 2.90.

According to the Philippine News Agency published in January 16, 2019, the 3rd Pangasinan Engineering District Office of the Department of Public Works and Highways (DPWH) has revealed the consummation of 306 infrastructure projects in the province of Pangasinan amounting to 3.14 billion pesos composed of 29 barangay health stations (BHS) and two (2) rural health units (RHU). The BHS and RHUs are located in San Quintin, Umingan, Bautista, Alcala, Urdaneta City, Balungao, Asingan, Villasis, Rosales, Pozzorubio, Natividad, Binalonan, Sta. Maria, Tayug, and San Nicolas. Out of the mentioned localities, five (5) were part of this research study: Balungao, San Nicolas, Tayug, Alcala, and Villasis.

Moreover, among the Department of Agriculture’s farm-to-market road projects, 17 were constructed. They are located in San Nicolas, Alcala, Binalonan, Bautista, Tayug, Balungao, Asingan, and Umingan, while two projects are still ongoing in Barangay Sta. Cruz Umingan and Laoac. Furthermore, 29 school building projects also in the 3rd Engineering district have been completed, while seven are still undergoing construction. The other projects in 2018 are those regular infrastructures such as flood control projects and road constructions and road widening (Austria, 2019).

At the bottom of the list is the area on Housing with a weighted mean of 2.64 having a verbal description of Moderate Extent. In 1992, the Republic Act No. 7279 otherwise known as the Act providing for a Comprehensive And Continuing Urban Development And Housing Program, Establish The Mechanism For Its Implementation was passed. Section 21 on the Government’s Role in Basic Services stipulates that Socialized housing or resettlement areas shall be furnished by the LGU or the National Housing Authority in partnership with the concerned agencies and private developers having the following basic services and facilities: a) Sewerage facilities and an efficient and adequate solid waste disposal system; b) Access to primary roads and transportation facilities; c) Potable water; and d) Power and electricity and an adequate power distribution system” (www.hudcc.gov.ph).

The law is explicit on the “cooperation” aspect of the above provisions. The LGU or the NHA must provide water, power, sewerage, waste disposal, and access (right-of-way) to primary roads. The developer is expected to build the socialized subdivision and the houses. However, the facilities and utilities are to be provided by either the LGU or the NHA. The housing unit is the government’s contribution to the “cooperative” partnership with the private sector (Caguining, 2015).

In an article published in the Manila Times, Tan (2015) mentioned that housing needs do not necessarily translate to an impressive demand because of the issue of affordability. The government must elevate those “underprivileged and homeless” members of our society to a level where they can afford the minimum design standard housing unit. Only then, their housing needs will become potent demand; and effective demand will drive up housing supply. It is where subsidy comes in – to influence the behavior of the “underprivileged and homeless” and give them access to the housing stock. It is our position that the state must step up its direct subsidy program because indirect subsidies are not enough. What is concerning us in the private sector is the seeming governmental attitude of passing on its obligation to provide housing for the poor by compelling developers to produce socialized housing, even if it is not in line with their business. This is the impetus for Sec. 18, RA 7279.

Significant Difference on the Assessment of the Three Groups of Respondents on the Delivery of Basic Services of the SGLG LGU Awardees

Based on the result, there is no significant difference in the response of the three groups of respondents on the extent of delivery of basic services of the SGLG LGU awardees ($F(2,372) = 0.265$, ns). The result is because the p-value or the significant value is greater than 0.05. These findings may be due to almost the same result of Mean among the three groups. It means that the data provide little or no evidence that the null hypothesis is false. Thus, there is no credible evidence or proof that the result provided by the three groups of respondents regarding the extent of service delivery of the SGLG LGU awardees can tell whether these LGUs undoubtedly give that kind of performance.

Table 2 Analysis of Variation Summary Result on the Significant Difference in the Assessment of the Three Groups of Respondents on the Extent of Delivery of Basic Services of the SGLG LGU Awardees

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p
Between Groups	0.067	2	0.033	0.265	0.769
Within Groups	3.400	27	0.126		
Total	3.467	29			

Significant at $p < 0.05$

3.1. Challenges Faced by the SGLG LGU Awardees in the Delivery of Basic Services

The main challenge faced by the LGU SGLG Awardees in the delivery of basic services is lack of public involvement in municipal planning and programs according to 50% of the 74 respondents. The Philippines has two most significant civil society classification, namely the Non-Government Organizations (NGOs) and the Peoples' Organizations (POs). In other countries, they are called community-based organizations.

People's organizations (POs) are generally made up of underprivileged individuals and labor to advance their members' substantial or social welfare. POs are grassroots institutions, and their constituents typically work through volunteerism. NGOs are mediators between the State and POs. They commend and work for needy individuals, who may not necessarily be members of their organizations. Several NGOs work to enhance the POs by providing financial support, undertaking advocacy, and establishing linkages. Added to to the involvement of volunteers, the NGOs also employ members of their staff. (ADB Report, 2007)

Table 3 Summary of Response on the Challenges Faced by the SGLG LGU Awardees in the Delivery of Basic Services n = 378

Challenges	f (%)			Total	Rank
	LGU N = 74	Barangay Officials N = 150	Residents N = 148		
inadequate skills development program	24 (32.4)	95 (63.3)	86 (58.1)	205	2
weak institutional management	11 (14.9)	44 (29.3)	68 (45.9)	123	11
political interference in municipal administration	21 (28.4)	39 (26.0)	49 (33.1)	109	15
lack of public involvement in municipal planning and programs.	37 (50.0)	86 (57.3)	86 (58.1)	209	1
inadequate allocation of funds	29 (39.2)	74 (49.3)	77 (52.0)	180	3
lack of genuine participation due to political instability	23 (31.1)	65 (43.3)	74 (50.0)	162	4
corruption and politicians' interference in the administration of the municipality	22 (29.7)	39 (26.0)	44 (37.2)	105	17
lack of relevant infrastructure in rural areas	30 (40.8)	49 (32.7)	56 (37.8)	135	8
inadequate provision of water	22 (29.7)	55 (36.7)	66 (44.6)	143	6
inadequate provision of electricity	13 (17.6)	43 (28.7)	60 (40.5)	116	13
inadequate sanitation	22 (29.7)	45 (30.0)	57 (38.5)	124	10
lack of adequate nutrition	16 (21.6)	38 (25.3)	52 (35.14)	106	16
lack of financial support/inadequate financial resources	24 (32.4)	74 (49.3)	56 (37.8)	154	5
shortage of human resources	21 (28.4)	44 (29.3)	56 (38.1)	121	12
unclear powers and functions to undertake service delivery	14 (18.9)	30 (20.0)	44 (29.7)	88	19
poor public-private partnership	17 (23.0)	44 (29.3)	52 (35.1)	113	14
inaccessibility of community for services	14 (18.9)	28 (18.7)	44 (29.7)	86	20
poor public participation	27 (36.5)	57 (38.0)	52 (35.1)	136	7
lacks the capacity to monitor and support local government	17 (23.0)	34 (22.7)	45 (30.4)	96	18
lack of controls and accountability	25 (33.8)	48 (32.0)	52 (35.1)	125	9

The result is a reflection that the SGLG-LGU Awardees have not fully activated their partnership with the different non-government organizations and civil society organizations, which was observed by the local government employees of the eight (8) localities involved in this study.

However, weak institutional management was only considered as a challenge in the delivery of basic government services by 11 or 14.9% of the respondents. Thus, the LGU respondents perceive that their LGU deserves the SGLG Award because of the good management of the local government unit.

On the side of the barangay officials, the main challenge they perceive to be faced by the SGLG LGU Awardees is on inadequate skills development program, as mentioned by 95 or 63.30% out of the 150 respondents. The barangay officials believe that there are employees and deliverers of the basic government services that do not possess the required skills. Nonetheless, the inaccessibility of community for services was declared by 28 or 18.7% of the respondents being the least of the challenge in the delivery of basic government services. It implies that very few of the barangay officials were unable to access the different basic government services as compared to the services that are being cascaded down to the barangays.

The Residents, on the other hand, revealed two (2) main challenges in the delivery of basic government services by the SGLG LGU Awardees, to wit: inadequate skills development program and lack of public involvement in municipal planning and programs. It is amusing to note that the two (2) challenges observed by the residents were the main challenges identified by the barangay officials and LGU respondents, respectively. Hence, the residents affirm the perception and observation of the other two groups of respondents that implementors of the delivery of basic government services do not have the necessary skills to implement the programs, and there is weak involvement of the community in the planning of the basic service programs.

Relatively, three (3) challenges were identified by 44 or 29.70% of the 148 respondents, as follows: corruption and politicians' interference in the administration of the municipality; unclear powers and functions to undertake service delivery; and inaccessibility of community for services. These three indicators insinuate that there are residents who have been exposed to these challenges and have observed that it affects the delivery of basic government services in their locality.

Table 4 Summary of Pearson Moment Correlation Analysis between the Challenges Faced and the Delivery of Basic Services by the SGLG LGU Awardees

		a	b	c	d	e	f	g	h	i	j
Delivery of Basic Services	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	-0.077	-0.262*	-0.199	-0.251*	-0.336**	-0.182	-0.312**	0.028	0.098	0.007
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.514	.0024	0.089	0.031	0.003	0.121	0.007	0.812	0.404	0.956
	N	74	74	74	74	74	74	74	74	74	74
	Relationship	NR	WR	NR	WR	MR	NR	MR	NR	NR	NR
		K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T
Delivery of Basic Services	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	-0.185	-0.084	-0.259*	-0.103	0.064	-0.048	-0.029	-0.139	0.069	-0.152
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.114	0.479	0.026	0.384	0.590	0.686	0.808	0.238	0.559	0.197
	N	74	74	74	74	74	74	74	74	74	74
	Relationship	NR	NR	WR	NR						

Legend: 0 = No Relationship (NR), 0.10-.29 =Weak Relationship (WR), 0.30-0.49 = Moderate Relationship (MR), 0.50-1.00 = Strong Relationship (SR) *. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed). **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Consequently, result shows that among the 20 listed challenges on the questionnaire, Lack of public involvement in municipal planning and programs emerged as the top one with 209 frequency of respondents, while the least is Inaccessibility to the community for services with only 86 respondents. The ranked one item is one of the most common challenges in LGUs, as validated by Enshassi et al. (2016). According to Enshassi et Al., the shortage of skills, the financial challenges, and the lack of interest and support from the city government were the main challenges to community participation.

Significant Relationship between the Delivery of Government Services and the Challenges Faced by the SGLG LGU Awardees in the Delivery of Basic Services

There exists a “Weak Negative Relationship” between the delivery of services and the challenges b. Weak institutional management and d. Lack of public involvement in municipal planning and programs. It means that the variables are inversely proportional to each other. The extent of delivery increases as weak institutional management decreases. It is apparent because as the institutional management becomes intense, the delivery of basic services most likely should increase. Also, the extent of delivery of basic services increases as the lack of public involvement in municipal planning and programs decreases. Results infer that the public should be more involved in government planning and programs in order for the delivery of services to increase.

Likewise, there exists a “Moderate Negative Relationship” between the delivery of basic services and the challenges e. Inadequate allocation of funds and g. Corruption and politicians’ interference in the administration of the municipality. It is an implication that the delivery of the SGLG LGU awardees of basic services increases as the allocation of funds becomes adequate or as the inadequacy of funds decreases. This finding is also the same as the other variable where the extent of delivery of basic services increases as the corruption and politicians’ interference in the administration decreases.

The correlation analysis implies that there is a negative relationship between the delivery of services and the challenges faced by the SGLG LGU awardees. The finding is true because the delivery of basic services of the government most likely should increase as the challenges they face decrease.

The results manifest that the more challenges the different SGLG LGU awardees will face, it will create a decline in the efficient and effective delivery of the basic government services to the beneficiaries. On the other hand, the more efficient and effective the delivery of services will be provided by the SGLG Awardees, the fewer challenges they would face because of the cooperation of all concerned stakeholders.

4. Conclusion

The local government units in the province of Pangasinan that have been awarded the Seal of Good Local Governance for three (3) consecutive years exhibited Full Extent Delivery in the area of Health Services only. There is no significant difference in the assessment of the three (3) groups of respondents relative to the delivery of basic government services by the SGLG LGU Awardees in the province of Pangasinan. The delivery of basic government services by the SGLG LGU Awardees is challenged by the lack of public involvement in municipal planning and programs. There exists a significant negative relationship between the delivery of basic services and some of the challenges faced by the SGLG LGU awardees, where the delivery of basic services increases as the challenges faced are decreased. In the end, what matters most is the fulfillment of the mandate of the local government units to provide and delivery the basic government services to the people at whatever cost.

This points to the findings that the Seal of Good Local Governance has not yet manifested its results on the LGU Awardees since the reflection of the respondents is a clear indication that the LGUs have to top up their programs and projects to address the needs of their constituents.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Contributions of Authors

The paper is the sole work of the author who handled the conceptualizing, preparing instruments, data gathering, statistical analysis and tabulating, interpreting of data.

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